

Figure S2: Phylogenetic hypothesis of *Teretrurus* based on three mitochondrial (12S r RNA, 16S rRNA, ND4) markers (mtDNA dataset). Values at the nodes indicate branch support values. Values towards the left of the nodes indicate posterior probabilities from the Bayesian Inference and values on the right of the nodes indicate bootstrap support values from the Maximum Likelihood analysis. Lineages highlighted in red indicate populations described here as new species.